

Some Practical Applications of the Simulation Smoother in State Space Modeling

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Abstract

After the well-known Kalman filter (KF) and Kalman smoother (KS) algorithms, the simulation smoother emerges as the next key algorithm for operationalizing a linear state space model (SSM) in SSM-based data analysis. The KF and KS are typically used for model fitting, forecasting, interpolation of the response variable, and the estimation and extrapolation of latent components in the model. The simulation smoother further enhances data analysis by enabling the drawing of random samples from the joint distribution of the latent states, conditioned on the observed data. This presentation will demonstrate how the simulation smoother can be applied to practical problems, such as obtaining global (as opposed to pointwise) confidence bands for the latent components in an SSM (e.g., global confidence band for the latent level of a series) and deriving the sampling distribution of a function of the response variable forecasts.

Key Words: Simulation Smoother, State Space Modeling, Global Confidence Bands

1. Introduction

Linear state space models (SSMs) are widely used to model longitudinal and time series measurements that are recorded on one or more (univariate or multivariate) continuous variables. As an example, consider an SSM:

$$\begin{array}{ll} y_t & = Z_t \alpha_t + \epsilon_t & \text{Observation Equation} \\ \alpha_{t+1} & = T_t \alpha_t + \eta_{t+1} & \text{State Equation} \\ \alpha_1 & \sim N(0, Q_1) & \text{Initial Condition} \end{array}$$

where y_t denote values of a time series at times $t = 1, 2, \dots, N$. In this model

- α_t , $t \geq 1$, is a sequence of latent vectors, called the states, and the linear combination $Z_t \alpha_t$ denotes its contribution to y_t . The second term in the observation equation, ϵ_t , denotes a sequence of independent, zero-mean, Gaussian noise sequence with variances σ_t^2 .
- The state equation describes the time evolution of the state vectors. The state vector at time $(t + 1)$, α_{t+1} , is a sum of two terms: $T_t \alpha_t$ (which is obtained by multiplying α_t by the so called state-transition-matrix, T_t) and a zero-mean, Gaussian disturbance vector η_{t+1} . The disturbance vectors η_t , $t \geq 1$ are assumed to be mutually independent, and independent of the observation noise sequence ϵ_t , $t \geq 1$.
- For the discussion in this article, we will assume that the vectors Z_t , the transition matrices T_t , the noise variances σ_t^2 , and the disturbance covariances $\text{Cov}(\eta_t) = Q_t$, are all known (or are already estimated from the data). In addition, the response variable values (y_t , $t = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are assumed to be known except for some select time points, where they can be missing.

In this setting, the well-known Kalman Filter (KF) and Kalman Smoother (KS) algorithms enable the computation of the conditional distributions of the latent vectors in the model, given the observed data. These distributions turn out to be Gaussian and therefore are fully determined by the conditional mean and covariance. The KF and KS algorithms provide:

- $\hat{\alpha}_t = E(\alpha_t | y_1, y_2, \dots, y_t)$ and $P_t = \text{Cov}(\alpha_t | y_1, y_2, \dots, y_t)$, which are the conditional mean and covariance of the latent state α_t , given the data up to time t . The conditional means, $\hat{\alpha}_t$, are called the filtered estimates of α_t .
- $\tilde{\alpha}_t = E(\alpha_t | y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N)$ and $V_t = \text{Cov}(\alpha_t | y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N)$, which are conditional mean and covariance of the latent state α_t , given all the observed data. The full-sample estimates $\tilde{\alpha}_t$ are called smoothed estimates.

The output of KF and KS is used for a variety of purposes. For example, model-based imputation of a missing response value at $t = t_1$ can be obtained as $\tilde{y}_{t_1} = Z_{t_1}' \tilde{\alpha}_{t_1}$ and the standard error of this estimate is obtained as the square root of $g_{t_1} = Z_{t_1}' V_{t_1} Z_{t_1}$. In many cases the elements of the state vector have natural interpretations and, after a suitable partitioning of Z_t and α_t , the observation equation has the form:

$$\begin{aligned} y_t &= Z_t^1 \alpha_t^1 + Z_t^2 \alpha_t^2 + \dots + \epsilon_t \\ y_t &= \mu_t + \omega_t + \dots + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

The linear combinations of the state elements, such as $\mu_t (= Z_t^1 \alpha_t^1)$, are called model components and can represent the time-varying level of the time series, or its seasonal pattern, and so on. In an obvious way, the KF and KS can provide the filtered and smoothed estimates (and their standard errors) of the model components at any given time point, t . While adequate in a large variety of applications, the KF and KS algorithms have one important limitation: they don't provide the joint conditional distribution of latent states at multiple time points, for example, they don't provide the joint conditional distribution of $(\alpha_{t_1}, \alpha_{t_2})$ given the data, at two different time points t_1 and t_2 and this means that we cannot use the KS output to obtain the standard error of $(\tilde{\mu}_{t_1} + \tilde{\mu}_{t_2})$, the sum of smoothed estimates of μ_t at time points t_1 and t_2 . The simulation smoother algorithm is useful in precisely such situations. It enables you to generate a random draw, $(\bar{\alpha}_1, \bar{\alpha}_2, \dots, \bar{\alpha}_N)$, from the joint conditional distribution of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_N)$ given the full sample $Y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N)$. By making a sufficiently large number of draws from the joint conditional distribution, you can obtain the sampling distribution of arbitrarily complex functions of the conditional estimates of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_N)$. The aim of this article is to illustrate some of the practical applications of simulation smoother.

In this section we have used a relatively simple form of SSM to illustrate the main concepts, while keeping the notational complexity to a minimum. The methodology discussed here is applicable to more general linear SSMs. A good reference for this methodology is the first part of (Durbin & Koopman, 2012). The state space modeling computations for the illustrative examples in this article are carried out using the CSSM procedure in SAS Viya/Econometrics® (see [PROC CSSM](#)).

2. Global Confidence Band for a Nonparametric Curve Estimate

The scatter plot shown in Figure 1 shows data from an example that discusses nonparametric curve estimation in (Givens & Hoeting, 2005). The data are 200 simulated values, y_t , generated according to the model:

$$y_t = f(t) + \epsilon_t, \quad \epsilon_t \sim N(0, \sigma_t^2)$$

Here $f(t)$, $0 \leq t \leq 1$, is a smooth function and the variance, σ_t^2 , of the independent, zero-mean, Gaussian noise sequence, ϵ_t , changes smoothly with t . These are longitudinal data, that is, the time index, t , is continuous and y_t are evaluated on an unequally spaced grid.

Figure 1

An example in the documentation of the CSSM procedure shows how you can obtain an estimate of $f(t)$ as a variable band-width, cubic smoothing spline (see [Variable Band-Width Smoother](#)). This is done by modeling y_t according to the following SSM:

$$\begin{aligned} y_t &= Z_t \alpha_t + \epsilon_t \\ &= \mu_t + \epsilon_t \\ \alpha_{t+h} &= T_t^{t+h} \alpha_t + \eta_{t+h} \end{aligned}$$

Here the latent state α_t is two dimensional (its first element, denoted by μ_t , represents $f(t)$ and the second element represents the derivative of $f(t)$), the row vector $Z_t = (1 \ 0)$, and the transition matrix, in row-major format, is $T_t^{t+h} = (1 \ h; 0 \ 1)$. For additional details about the covariance and variance of the disturbances η_t and ϵ_t , see [Variable Band-Width Smoother](#). After fitting this model to the data, you can obtain the filtered and smoothed estimates of μ_t and their standard errors. Figure 2 shows the smoothed estimate $\tilde{\mu}_t$, the pointwise 95% confidence band ($\tilde{\mu}_t \pm 1.96 * SE_t$), where SE_t denotes the standard error of $\tilde{\mu}_t$, and the response values y_t . The values of $\tilde{\mu}_t$ and their standard errors SE_t are provided by the Kalman smoother.

Figure 2

In some applications a pointwise confidence band is not adequate, and a more global confidence band is needed. For such situations, you can work with confidence bands based on the simulation smoother. This is done as follows:

- Draw a sufficiently large number (say 10,000) of random draws, $(\bar{\alpha}_{t_1}, \bar{\alpha}_{t_2}, \dots, \bar{\alpha}_{t_{200}})_i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 10000$, from the joint conditional distribution of $(\alpha_{t_1}, \alpha_{t_2}, \dots, \alpha_{t_{200}})$ given the full sample $Y = (y_{t_1}, y_{t_2}, \dots, y_{t_{200}})$. Of course, this also provides 10,000 random draws—random trajectories—of smoothed estimates of μ_t : $(\bar{\mu}_{t_1}, \dots, \bar{\mu}_{t_{200}})_i$, $i = 1, \dots, 10000$.
- You can now use this large sample of trajectories to determine the coverage of any given confidence band. For example, you can compute the proportion of trajectories that are entirely within the pointwise 95% confidence band $(\bar{\mu}_t \pm 1.96 * SE_t)$. It turns out that only 909 out of 10,000 trajectories lie entirely within this band. Therefore, the global confidence associated with the pointwise 95% confidence band is only about 10 percent! The situation improves considerably if we slightly widen the band as $(\bar{\mu}_t \pm 3.36 * SE_t)$. In this case, 9560 out of 10,000 trajectories lie entirely within this widened band. That is, the global confidence associated with this wider band exceeds 95%. Figure 3 summarizes this information.

Figure 3

Figure 3 shows that only a slight widening of the confidence band allows us to make a much stronger statement about the estimated curve. This is possible only because the simulation smoother enabled us to draw large number of samples from the joint conditional distribution of latent states given the data and that allowed us to calculate the precise coverage probability of any band.

3. SSM-Based Stochastic Claims Reserving

The data in Table1 shows yearly claims paid by a fictional auto-insurer over a stretch of 10 years. For accidents that occur each year (accident year), claims are made by the policy holders in that and subsequent years, which are called development years for that accident year. The individual cells of the table, x_{ij} , denote the total claims paid by the insurer for an accident year i and development year j ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 10$ and $j = 0, 1, \dots, 9$). In the claims reserving literature, x_{ij} , are called incremental claims. Note that, by the 10th year, only the upper left triangle of the table is filled with the claims incurred. The remaining part of the table (the shaded lower right triangle) is unobserved and filled in for the subsequent 9 years. To comply with the regulatory guidelines and their own business needs, the insurers must reserve adequate capital to satisfy the total future claims, R , which is the sum of x_{ij} in the shaded triangle, that is, $R = \sum x_{ij}$ (the sum being over unobserved elements in the shaded region). This is the well-known claims-reserving problem. Since the future is uncertain and the cost of under/over-reservation can be high, a point estimate, \hat{R} , of the reserve is not enough. The sampling distribution of \hat{R} is needed. Usually a higher quantile, such as 75th percentile, of the sampling distribution of \hat{R} is the recommended reserve value.

Incremental Claim Amounts For an Auto Insurer
The Values in the Colored Cells are in the Future (Unobserved)

Accident Year	Dev Year 0	Dev Year 1	Dev Year 2	Dev Year 3	Dev Year 4	Dev Year 5	Dev Year 6	Dev Year 7	Dev Year 8	Dev Year 9
1	2501022	2341440	1007622	546127	288321	161933	74853	37950	21906	7010
2	2899865	2604053	1155090	617014	329631	161943	81413	38986	19314	10083
3	3267626	2795565	1258188	650052	329904	158629	75974	40778	17968	11933
4	3273441	2753362	1227563	638982	305488	147298	77662	41554	23647	8963
5	3652121	2986067	1322326	656965	320117	163935	85048	39681	18704	9869
6	3993680	3209022	1351929	676403	342434	176461	92824	43870	18466	13409
7	4432543	3350567	1366866	734163	400471	190999	84350	42497	21410	14401
8	4604762	3253448	1375894	748949	393260	196828	102873	50581	36167	15463
9	4556591	3119034	1393514	757094	426651	201507	99973	54631	27048	14157
10	4454117	3035876	1342558	784309	423950	200252	90238	48777	25829	16916

Table 1: Incremental Claims

There are many claims reserving methods used in the insurance industry. Because of the longitudinal nature of the claims data, SSM-based modeling is a natural fit for this problem and a variety of SSMs are proposed in the literature for claims data modeling. As an illustration, we will analyze these data using an SSM proposed in (Verral, 1994). This SSM is slightly involved and will not be described here. For a more detailed discussion of the claims reserving based on SSMs, see [SSM-Based Claims Reserving](#) and the references therein.

The SSM proposed in (Verral, 1994) models $y_{ij} = \log(\text{IncrementalClaims}) = \log(x_{ij})$. In this model the data are processed by calendar years, that is, as the claims are recorded each year. In this case, the first year has one value $y_1 = (y_{10})$, the second year has two values $y_2 = (y_{20}, y_{11})$, and so on. These values represent diagonals from lower left to upper right in Table 1. A table like Table 1, that contains 10 years of historical data and 9 years of future data, leads to the time series $(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{19})$ where the first ten y-vectors (which are of differing sizes) contain the historical data, and the subsequent nine y-vectors contain missing values that need to be forecast based on the fitted SSM. Exponentiating these forecasts and adding them up gives a point estimate of the needed reserve: $\hat{R} = \sum \hat{x}_{ij} = \sum \exp(\hat{y}_{ij})$. The next three tables, Table 2 to Table 4, show these steps of log-transforming of incremental claims, forecasting these log-transformed incremental claims according to the fitted SSM, and finally obtaining a point forecast of the claims reserve $\hat{R} = 11.83$ million. The fitting and forecasting of the time series according to the SSM proposed in (Verral, 1994) is done using the KF and KS algorithms. However, because \hat{R} is a sum of exponentiated forecasts, its sampling distribution is intractable. This is yet another important use case for the simulation smoother.

Log(Incremental Claims)

1

Accident Year	Dev Year 0	Dev Year 1	Dev Year 2	Dev Year 3	Dev Year 4	Dev Year 5	Dev Year 6	Dev Year 7	Dev Year 8	Dev Year 9
1	14.73221	14.666277	13.823104	13.210607	12.57183	11.994938	11.223281	10.544025	9.9945159	8.855093
2	14.880175	14.77258	13.959689	13.332647	12.705729	11.995	11.30729	10.570958	9.8685855	.
3	14.999574	14.843545	14.045183	13.384808	12.706557	11.974323	11.238146	10.615898	.	.
4	15.001352	14.828333	14.020541	13.367632	12.629666	11.900213	11.260121	.	.	.
5	15.110819	14.909468	14.094903	13.395386	12.676442	12.007225
6	15.200224	14.981477	14.117043	13.424544	12.743834
7	15.304484	15.02464	14.128031	13.506486
8	15.342602	14.995226	14.134614
9	15.332085	14.953034
10	15.309339

Table 2: Log(Incremental Claims)

Verral Model-Based Predictions

1

Accident Year	Dev Year 0	Dev Year 1	Dev Year 2	Dev Year 3	Dev Year 4	Dev Year 5	Dev Year 6	Dev Year 7	Dev Year 8	Dev Year 9
1	14.73221	14.666277	13.823104	13.210607	12.57183	11.994938	11.223281	10.544025	9.9945159	8.855093
2	14.880175	14.77258	13.959689	13.332647	12.705729	11.995	11.30729	10.570958	9.8685855	8.9931913
3	14.999574	14.843545	14.045183	13.384808	12.706557	11.974323	11.238146	10.615898	9.9823392	9.1019837
4	15.001352	14.828333	14.020541	13.367632	12.629666	11.900213	11.260121	10.628551	9.9937522	9.1133968
5	15.110819	14.909468	14.094903	13.395386	12.676442	12.007225	11.367455	10.736019	10.101221	9.2208655
6	15.200224	14.981477	14.117043	13.424544	12.743834	12.097766	11.457956	10.82652	10.191722	9.3113666
7	15.304484	15.02464	14.128031	13.506486	12.845681	12.199157	11.559347	10.927911	10.293113	9.4127572
8	15.342602	14.995226	14.134614	13.545352	12.884159	12.237635	11.597825	10.966389	10.331591	9.4512355
9	15.332085	14.953034	14.126173	13.53628	12.875087	12.228562	11.588752	10.957316	10.322518	9.4421626
10	15.309339	14.93234	14.104833	13.514939	12.853746	12.207221	11.567411	10.935976	10.301177	9.420822

Table 3: Predicted log(Incremental Claims)

Accident Year	Dev Year 0	Dev Year 1	Dev Year 2	Dev Year 3	Dev Year 4	Dev Year 5	Dev Year 6	Dev Year 7	Dev Year 8	Dev Year 9
1	2501022	2341440	1007622	546127	288321	161933	74853	37950	21906	7010
2	2899865	2604053	1155090	617014	329631	161943	81413	38986	19314	8048.1001
3	3267626	2795565	1258188	650052	329904	158629	75974	40778	21640.875	8973.0749
4	3273441	2753362	1227563	638982	305488	147298	77662	41297.225	21889.278	9076.0718
5	3652121	2986067	1322326	656965	320117	163935	86461.525	45982.645	24372.75	10105.807
6	3993680	3209022	1351929	676403	342434	179470.5	94651.399	50338.248	26681.404	11063.057
7	4432543	3350567	1366866	734163	379147.74	198621.58	104751.54	55709.782	29528.544	12243.583
8	4604762	3253448	1375894	763258.79	394021	206413.14	108860.75	57895.174	30686.895	12723.876
9	4556591	3119034	1364329	756365.14	390462.26	204548.84	107877.53	57372.273	30409.735	12608.955
10	4454117	3055153	1335521.9	740394.86	382217.84	200229.89	105599.75	56160.885	29767.648	12342.723

Table 4: Inverse Predictions of log(Incremental Claims) and their sum

The steps of obtaining the sampling distribution of $\hat{R} = \sum \hat{x}_{ij} = \sum \exp(\hat{y}_{ij})$ are as follows:

- Using simulation smoother, draw a sufficiently large number of random draws (say 10,000) of forecasts $(\hat{y}_{11}, \hat{y}_{12}, \dots, \hat{y}_{19})_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, 10000$.
- By inverse transforming these forecasts and summing them, we get 10,000 random draws of \hat{R} . These provide us with the simulation-based sampling distribution of \hat{R} .

The histogram in Figure 4 shows the histogram of these \hat{R} values. Since we have used simulated data in this example, we know the true future values and therefore the true R value, which is about 11.85 million. A heuristic claims reserving method, called Chain Ladder method, is quite popular in reserving practice. In this example, we use it as a benchmark method. The Chain Ladder estimate and its standard error, are calculated using an R package, also called ChainLadder (see [ChainLadder](#)). The true R value, 11.85 million, ChainLadder predicted R value 12.91 million and, ChainLadder predicted R value plus its standard error, 13.47 million are shown with reference lines in the histogram. The mean and a few percentiles of the simulation-based sampling distribution of \hat{R} are shown below:

Mean	Median	Q1	Q3	P90
11.91	11.89	11.57	12.26	13.50

This shows that the recommended reserve value according to Verral’s model for these data, 12.26 million (75th percentile), is quite adequate while being much lower than the recommended reserve value according to ChainLadder, 13.47 million.

Figure 4

Summary

After the well-known Kalman filter (KF) and Kalman smoother (KS) algorithms, the simulation smoother emerges as the next key algorithm for operationalizing a linear state space model (SSM) in SSM-based data analysis. The KF and KS are typically used for model fitting, forecasting, interpolation of the response variable, and the estimation and extrapolation of latent components in the model. The simulation smoother further enhances data analysis by enabling the drawing of random samples from the joint distribution of the latent states, conditioned on the observed data. This article showed two practical applications of simulation smoother. Simulation smoother is useful in many other cases, including importance sampling based nonlinear state space modeling.

Disclaimer

The views and opinions expressed in this article are solely those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of the author's employer.

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